

Extension of Binomial Series with Optimized Binomial Coefficient

Chinnaraji Annamalai

School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India

Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: This paper presents the binomial expansion and series with optimized binomial coefficients. The binomial series is built on the building blocks of optimized binomial coefficients and multiple summations of geometric series.

MSC Classification codes: 05A10, 40A05 (65B10)

Keywords: binomial expansion, geometric series, computation

1. Introduction

The binomial expansion [1, 2] and series have been constituted using multiple summations of geometric series [3-9] and optimized binomial coefficients. In the earlier days, geometric series with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus and as an introduction to Taylor series and Fourier series. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [18,19].

2. Optimized Binomial Coefficient

The following binomial coefficient [10-12] is named as optimized binomial coefficient V_r^n , which is the extension of traditional binomial coefficient.

$$V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\cdots(r+n)}{n!} = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{r+i}{n!} \quad (n \geq 1, r \geq 0 \text{ \& } n, r \in N).$$
$$V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)\cdots(n+r)}{r!} = \prod_{j=1}^r \frac{n+j}{r!} \quad (n \geq 0, r \geq 1 \text{ \& } n, r \in N).$$

$$V_r^n = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{r+i}{n!} = V_n^r = \prod_{j=1}^r \frac{n+j}{r!} \quad (n, r \geq 1 \text{ \& } n, r \in N),$$

The traditional binomial coefficient is given below:

$$\binom{n}{r} = nC_r = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}, \quad (n \geq r \text{ \& } n, r \in N),$$

where $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$ and $n!$ denotes the factorial of n .

The comparison between optimized and traditional coefficients is given below:

$$V_x^y = V_y^x \text{ denotes the optimized combination. Let } z = x + y. \text{ Then, } zC_x = zC_y.$$

For example,

$$V_3^5 = V_5^3 = (5+3)C_3 = (5+3)C_5 = 56.$$

Also, $V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = \frac{n!}{n!0!} = 1$ and $V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1$ ($\because 0! = 1$).
 Note that both V_r^n and nC_r are not equal.

The following binomial identity of optimized binomial coefficients plays a vital role in the construction of binomial expansion and series.

$$V_0^p + V_1^p + V_2^p + V_3^p + \dots + V_r^p = V_r^{p+1} \Rightarrow \sum_{i=0}^r V_i^p = V_r^{p+1} \quad (p, r \in N).$$

The binomial series mentioned below is built on the optimized coefficients and geometric series [13-17].

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r \frac{1}{x^i} = 1 + V_1^r \frac{1}{x} + V_2^r \frac{1}{x^2} + V_3^r \frac{1}{x^3} + \dots + V_{n-1}^r \frac{1}{x^{n-1}} + V_n^r \frac{1}{x^n} \quad (\because V_0^r = 1).$$

By substituting $r = 1$ in this binomial identity we get

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^1 \frac{1}{x^i} = \sum_{i=0}^n (i+1) \frac{1}{x^i} = 1 + \frac{2}{x} + \frac{3}{x^2} + \dots + \frac{n}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{(n+1)}{x^n} \quad (\because V_0^1 = 1).$$

that is, $1 + \frac{2}{x} + \frac{3}{x^2} + \dots + \frac{n}{x^{n-1}} + \frac{(n+1)}{x^n} = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)}{x^i} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^1 \frac{1}{x^i}$.

3. Binomial Expansion

The following binomial expansions are derived from the binomial identity $\sum_{i=0}^r V_i^p = V_r^{p+1}$.

$$(1). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)}{1!} = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n + (n+1) = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)}{2!}.$$

$$(2). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)}{2!} = 1 + 3 + 6 + \dots + \frac{(n+1)(n+2)}{2!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)}{3!}.$$

$$(3). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)}{3!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)}{4!}.$$

$$(4). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3)(i+4)}{4!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)}{5!}.$$

Similarly, this process continues upto r times. The r^{th} binomial expansion is as follows:

$$(r). \quad \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(i+1)(i+2)(i+3) \dots (i+r)}{r!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2) \dots (n+r)(n+r+1)}{(r+1)!}.$$

4. Binomial Theorem

The binomial theorem states that multiple summations of geometric series with optimized binomial coefficients refer to a binomial series,

$$\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} \frac{1}{x^i} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r \frac{1}{x^i} + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^r \frac{1}{x^i} + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^r \frac{1}{x^i} + \dots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^r \frac{1}{x^i} + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^r \frac{1}{x^i}.$$

Proof: Let's show that the computation of binomial series (right-hand side of the theorem) is equal to the summation of binomial series for upper limit $r+1$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r \frac{1}{x^i} + \sum_{i=1}^n V_{i-1}^r \frac{1}{x^i} + \sum_{i=2}^n V_{i-2}^r \frac{1}{x^i} + \cdots + \sum_{i=n-1}^n V_{i-(n-1)}^r \frac{1}{x^i} + \sum_{i=n}^n V_{i-n}^r \frac{1}{x^i} \\
 &= \left(V_0^r + V_1^r \frac{1}{x} + V_2^r \frac{1}{x^2} + V_3^r \frac{1}{x^3} + \cdots + V_n^r \frac{1}{x^n} \right) + \left(V_0^r \frac{1}{x} + V_1^r \frac{1}{x^2} + V_2^r \frac{1}{x^3} + V_3^r \frac{1}{x^4} + \cdots + V_{n-1}^r \frac{1}{x^n} \right) \\
 &+ \left(V_0^r \frac{1}{x^2} + V_1^r \frac{1}{x^3} + V_2^r \frac{1}{x^4} + V_3^r \frac{1}{x^5} + \cdots + V_{n-2}^r \frac{1}{x^n} \right) + \cdots + \left(V_0^r \frac{1}{x^{n-1}} + V_1^r \frac{1}{x^n} \right) + V_0^r \frac{1}{x^n} \\
 &= V_0^r + (V_0^r + V_1^r) \frac{1}{x} + (V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r) \frac{1}{x^2} + \cdots + (V_0^r + V_1^r + V_2^r + V_3^r + \cdots + V_n^r) \frac{1}{x^n} \\
 & \text{(Note that } V_0^p + V_1^p + V_2^p + \cdots + V_r^p = V_r^{p+1} \text{ for } r = 1, 2, 3, \dots, \text{ and } V_0^p = V_0^{p+1} = 1) \\
 &= V_0^{r+1} + V_1^{r+1} \frac{1}{x} + V_2^{r+1} \frac{1}{x^2} + V_3^{r+1} \frac{1}{x^3} + V_4^{r+1} \frac{1}{x^4} + \cdots + V_{n-1}^{r+1} \frac{1}{x^{n-1}} + V_n^{r+1} \frac{1}{x^n} \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{r+1} \frac{1}{x^i}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, binomial coefficients, identities, expansions, theorems, and their proofs have been introduced for researchers who are working in computing and computational science. These results are built based on the multiple summation of geometrics.

References

- [1] Annamalai C (2022) "Annamalai's Binomial Identity and Theorem", SSRN Electronoc Journal. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4097907>.
- [2] Annamalai C (2022) "Combinatorial Relation of Optimized Combination with Permutation", OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ymk8b>.
- [3] Annamalai C (2022) "Computation of multiple binomial Series based on geometric series", Authorea. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.165057532.28448023/v1>.
- [4] Annamalai C (2017) "Computational modelling for the formation of geometric series using Annamalai computing method", Jñānābha, Vol. 47(2), pp 327-330. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/kwmcv>.
- [5] Annamalai C (2018) "Annamalai's Computing Model for Algorithmic Geometric Series and its Mathematical Structures", Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science, Vol.3 (1), pp 1-6. <https://www.doi.org/10.11648/j.mcs.20180301.11>.
- [6] Annamalai C (2022) "Analysis and Computation of Extended Geometric Series and Summability", OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/7h5ks>.

- [7] Annamalai C (2022) “Multiple summations of a geometric series and its binomial series”, Authorea. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.165029620.03276674/v1>.
- [8] Annamalai C (2018) “Algorithmic Computation of Annamalai’s Geometric Series and Summability”, Mathematics and Computer Science, Vol. 3(5), pp 100-101. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.mcs.20180305.11>.
- [9] Annamalai C (2022) “Annamalai Computing Method for Formation of Geometric Series using in Science and Technology”, International Journal for Science and Advance Research in Technology, Vol. 3(8), pp 287-289. <http://ijsart.com/Content/PDFDocuments/IJSARTV3I81725763643337779815308.pdf>.
- [10] Annamalai C (2019) “A Model of Iterative Computations for Recursive Summability”, Oxford Journal of Information and Mathematical Sciences, Vol. 33(1), pp 75-77. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.165167013.33544978/v1>.
- [11] Annamalai C (2020) “Optimized Computing Technique for Combination in Combinatorics”, hal-0286583. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9p4ek>
- [12] Annamalai C (2020) “Novel Computing Technique in Combinatorics”, hal-02862222. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m9re5>
- [13] Annamalai C (2022) “Sum of Geometric Series with Negative Exponents”, OpenAIRE. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6472535>
- [14] Annamalai C (2022) “Comparison between Optimized and Traditional Combinations of Combinatorics”, OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2qdyz>
- [15] Annamalai C (2022) “Novel Binomial Series and its Summations”, Authorea Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.164933885.53684288/v2>
- [16] Annamalai C (2017) “Analysis and Modelling of Annamalai Computing Geometric Series and Summability”, Mathematical Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences,6(1), 11-15. <https://doi.org/10.15415/mjis.2017.61002>.
- [17] Annamalai C (2009) “A Computational Geometric Series Method”, CiteSeerx. <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/summary?doi=10.1.1.148.5800>.
- [18] Annamalai C (2015) “Analysis of Heart Rhythms using Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set”, Journal of International Research in Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vol. 3(3), pp 72-76. <https://archives.biciconference.co.in/index.php/JIRMEPS/article/view/1124>.
- [19] Annamalai C (2010) “Application of Exponential Decay and Geometric Series in Effective Medicine”, Advances in Bioscience and Biotechnology, Vol. 1(1), pp 51-54. <https://doi.org/10.4236/abb.2010.11008>.